

RESOURCE-USE EFFICIENCY AND PROFITABILITY OF LOWLAND RICE FARMING IN EBONYI NORTH, NIGERIA

Esheya Samuel Esheya

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension
National Open University of Nigeria, Kaduna Campus

Email: sesheya@noun.edu.ng

<https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.032606010.12>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the resource-use efficiency and profitability of lowland rice farming in Ebonyi North, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, and primary data were collected from one hundred (100) sampled lowland rice farmers using structured questionnaires. Descriptive statistics, budgetary analysis, Cobb–Douglas ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, and marginal value product to marginal factor cost (MVP/MFC) ratios were used for data analysis. The Cobb–Douglas results showed that farm size, labour, seed, fertilizer, and agrochemicals had positive and statistically significant effects on rice output, with the model explaining a substantial proportion of the variation in production. The estimated returns to scale indicated increasing returns, suggesting that farmers could enhance output through expanded and more efficient input use. Allocative efficiency analysis revealed under-utilization of land, labour, and fertilizer, and over-utilization of seed and agrochemicals, implying sub-optimal resource allocation among farmers. Budgetary analysis demonstrated that lowland rice farming is profitable in the study area, with positive net farm income, a benefit–cost ratio greater than unity, and a favorable return on investment. Despite this profitability, inefficiencies in input use constrain potential income gains. The study therefore concludes that improving input allocation, strengthening extension services, and facilitating farmers' access to productive resources would enhance efficiency and profitability of lowland rice production in the study area.

KEYWORDS: Resource use, Efficiency, Profitability, Lowland rice, Production

INTRODUCTION

Rice is a major staple food and an important contributor to agricultural employment, income generation, and food security in Nigeria. Rising population growth and changing consumption patterns have significantly increased the demand for rice, making improved productivity and efficient resource utilization central to national food policy. Evidence shows that rice production

contributes substantially to household food requirements and agricultural GDP, thereby positioning the crop as a strategic commodity for economic development and poverty reduction (Gama et al., 2022). Despite its importance, rice productivity in Nigeria remains below potential due to sub-optimal input use, poor access to credit, limited extension services, and low adoption of improved technologies.

Empirical studies across Nigerian rice-producing regions indicate that farm size, labour, agrochemicals, fertilizer, and seed quantity significantly influence output and profitability, while inefficient allocation of these inputs constrains performance (Chidiebere-Mark et al., 2019). Rice has emerged as a crucial strategic and everyday staple crop in many nations, including Nigeria. Growing rice in wetlands, like river and mountain valleys, is known as lowland rice farming. It makes up over half of the nation's total rice production, making it a significant contributor. The primary production regions are in the southern states of Ebonyi, Enugu, and Cross-River, and in the Northern regions surrounding the Niger, Benue, and Kaduna rivers (Esheya, 2024). After maize and cassava, rice is the third most consumed staple grain in Nigeria. Because of its growing importance in the nation, it has become a crop of greatest importance for food security (Ume et al., 2017). Despite Nigeria's impressive production achievements, the country's constantly rising consumption rates cannot be reconciled with domestic output (CBN, 2018).

Ebonyi State is recognized as a major rice-producing area in southeastern Nigeria, with widespread cultivation across swamp, lowland, and upland ecologies. However, production has not met rising demand, largely because of low yield associated with weak adoption of improved production technologies and knowledge gaps along the rice value chain. Studies conducted within the state reveal variability in profitability across production systems, with swamp and lowland rice systems generally yielding higher returns than upland systems. Nonetheless, constraints such as limited access to credit, climate variability, and production inefficiencies continue to undermine optimal performance (Ogisi et al., 2012). Further evidence on efficiency

levels shows that only a small proportion of rice farmers in Ebonyi State operate at full technical efficiency, while the majority experience increasing returns to scale an indication that better resource allocation and improved management practices could substantially raise productivity and profitability.

Although lowland rice farming holds strong potential for improving food security and rural livelihoods in Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone, farmers still face persistent inefficiencies in the use of critical production resources such as land, labour, fertilizer, and capital. National and regional studies consistently report under-utilization or misallocation of inputs, inadequate extension support, and financial constraints that limit productivity gains and profitability in rice production systems. Within Ebonyi State specifically, declining productivity, low technological adoption, and limited technical efficiency among farmers suggest that available resources are not being optimally utilized to achieve maximum output and income. Consequently, there is a clear need for location-specific empirical evidence on the efficiency and profitability of lowland rice farming in Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone. Such information is essential for guiding policy interventions, improving resource allocation, enhancing farmer income, and strengthening food security in the region. Thus, this study evaluated the resource use and profitability of the lowland rice farming in Ebonyi North, Nigeria. Its specific goals were to: (i) describe the socioeconomic characteristics of lowland rice farmers, (ii) ascertain the allocative efficiency of the lowland rice production system, and (iii) estimate the profitability of lowland rice production system in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone of Ebonyi State, Nigeria, an area noted for rice cultivation and profitability differences across production systems. Evidence from studies in the state shows that rice farming, particularly under lowland systems can generate substantial returns on investment, indicating the economic relevance of the zone for efficiency analysis. A state in southeast Nigeria, Ebonyi is separated into thirteen local government areas and three agricultural zones: Ebonyi Central, Ebonyi South, and Ebonyi North. The local government areas of Abakaliki, Ebonyi, Izzi, and Ohaukwu are all included in the Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone. The state is located between $\sim 5-6^{\circ}\text{N}$, $7-8^{\circ}\text{E}$; temperature $\sim 28^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Nigeria's humid tropical agro-ecological zone. Its estimated population is 2,253,140, and its land area is 5,935 km². Benue State borders the state to the north, Enugu State borders it to the west, Cross River State borders it to the east, and Imo and Abia State border it to the south. A humid tropical environment is what Ebonyi State experiences. The average yearly temperature is 28°C , and there is between 1200 and 2500 mm of precipitation (NPC, 2006). The majority of Ebonyi is an agricultural area. It is one of Nigeria's top producers of cassava, rice, yam, potatoes, maize, and beans. The state's three agricultural zones are mostly used for the cultivation of rice, cassava and yams (EBADP, 2020, Esheya, 2021). Respondents for this study were chosen using multi-stage random sampling and purposeful sampling procedures. The first stage of the sampling procedure involved the purposive selection of major rice-producing Local Government Areas and communities within Ebonyi North. This

stage can be justified as a form of cluster sampling because the study area is naturally divided into geographical and administrative clusters (LGAs and farming communities); and only clusters with significant lowland rice production are relevant to the research objectives on resource-use efficiency and profitability. After defining relevant clusters, the selection of farmers within chosen communities was done using simple random sampling, which qualifies as probability sampling because each farmer had a known and non-zero chance of selection from the sampling frame. Again, randomization minimizes researcher bias in respondent selection.

There were twenty settlements in stage 1, five of which were purposefully chosen from each of the four local government areas. In order to obtain a sample size of one hundred (100) respondents for the study, five lowland rice farmers were chosen at random from each of the twenty communities in stage two using:

Yamane Formula:
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad n = 1 + N(e)^2 N \quad \dots (1)$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = total population size (300)

e = level of precision (sampling error), usually 0.05 for a 95% confidence level.

This gives.

$$n = 300 / (1 + 300(0.1)^2) = 100$$

Although the study employed 100 farm-level observations, which meets the basic rule-of-thumb for OLS estimation (generally $\geq 10-20$ observations per parameter), this sample size is relatively modest for efficiency analysis involving five production inputs. A limited sample may reduce statistical power to detect small

but meaningful input effects and precision of coefficient estimates. Accordingly, the results were interpreted with cautious generalization beyond the study population. Information on primary data was obtained through an oral interview and a standardized questionnaire from the list of registered rice farmers obtained from Ebonyi State Agricultural Development Programme (EBADP) in Ebonyi North zone. A variety of literature sources, including published and unpublished survey papers, journals, textbooks, the internet, conferences, and other publications, were used to gather secondary data for this study. The frequency distribution and percentage replies were used to examine objective (i), while costs and return analysis and the allocative efficiency model were used to assess objectives (ii) and (iii).

Model Specification

Cobb–Douglas Production Function

$$[Y = A X_1^{b_1} X_2^{b_2} X_3^{b_3} X_4^{b_4} X_5^{b_5} e^{\{u\}}] \dots (1)$$

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, \dots + e) \dots (2)$$

Where:

- (Y) = rice output
- (X₁)–(X₅) = land, labour, seed, fertilizer and agrochemicals.
- (b_i) = parameters to be estimated
- (u) = error term

This functional form is widely applied in rice-production efficiency studies in Nigeria (Ubokudom et al., 2022).

Allocative Efficiency

Allocative efficiency is calculated by MVP/MFC (3)

The Allocative efficiency was determined by equating the marginal value product of the resource to its unit price.

$$MVP = p_y f_i = p_{x_i} \dots (4)$$

$f_i = dy/dx$ which is the marginal physical product of the resource. The models were specified as follows:

$$r = MVP/MFC \dots (5)$$

$$MVP = \beta_i \times (Y/X_i) \times P_y \dots (6)$$

Where: r = efficiency ratio notation, MVP = marginal value product, MFC = marginal factor cost (cost of unit price of a particular input), MPP = marginal physical product and are arithmetic means of the yield, P_y = unit price of output, x_i = various input 1 to n = absolute value of % change in MVP of i^{th} resource, r_i = ratio of MVP to MFC for i^{th} resource, 100 = factor (percentage)

D_i = Absolute value of % change in MVP of i^{th} resource.

P_{x_i} is the unit price of the i^{th} resource

Y and X = are arithmetic mean of the yield and inputs considered respectively.

If $r = 1$, it implies that resources are efficiently used i.e. $MVP = MFC = 1$

$r > 1$, implies that resources are under-utilized

$r < 1$, implies that resources are over-utilized.

Budgetary (Profitability) Analysis

Profitability (net returns) is obtained by deducting the total cost of production from the total revenue. It is represented by the formula:

$$\text{Profitability} = TR - TC \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

where TR is total revenue, and TC is total cost.

$$TR = P Q \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

Equation (9) indicates that TR is the product of output price and quantity of output produced.

Also,

$$TC = TVC + TFC \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

where TVC is total variable cost and TFC is the total fixed cost.

$$\text{Gross margin} = (\text{G.M.}) = TR - TVC \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

$$\text{i.e. G.M} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i Q_i - \sum_{j=1}^m r_j x_j \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

Therefore, profitability (net income) can be calculated by gross margin less fixed input. The net farm income can be expressed as thus:

$$\text{NFI} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i Q_i - \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^m r_j x_j \right) + k \right] \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

Where: GM = Gross margin (N), NFI = Net farm income (N), P1 = Market (unit) price of output (N), Q = Quantity of output (kg), ri = Unit price of the variable input (kg), xi = quantity of the variable input (kg), K = Annual fixed cost (depreciation) (N), i = 1 2 3 n, j = 1 2 3.

$$\text{Also, profitability (net income) can be deduced as } PQ - TVC - TFC \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

Returns per Naira invested can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Returns/GHC} = \text{net income/TC} \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

Note that the expenses of rice seed, fertilizer, labor for weeding, fertilizer application, pesticides and herbicides, harvesting, and other goods and services (transportation) make up the study's total

variable cost. Similarly, land rent and the depreciated costs of farm equipment (such as the hoe, knife, drinkers, and wheelbarrow) are included in the total fixed cost components.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Lowland Rice Farmers**

S/N	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age (years)		
	20 – 30	6	6.0
	31 – 40	31	31.0
	41 – 50	40	40.0
	51 – 60	18	18.0
	61 and above	5	5.0
2.	Sex		
	Male	82	82.0
	Female	18	18.0
3.	Household size		
	1-5	6	6.0
	6-10	32	32.0
	11 and above	62	62.0
4.	Qualifications		
	No formal education	16	16.0
	Primary	24	24.0
	Secondary	53	53.0
	Tertiary	7	7.0
5.	Membership of cooperatives societies		
	Yes	86	86.0
	No	14	14.0
6.	Farm Size (ha)		
	0.5 -1.00	22	22.0
	1.1 – 2.00	40	40.0
	2.1 – 3.00	18	18.0
	3.1 – 4.00	12	12.0
	4.1 – 5.00	8	8.0
	5.1 and above	-	-

7.	Seed Type Used		
	Improved	82	82.0
	Local	18	18.0
8.	Labour Type Used		
	Family labour	34	34.0
	Hired	21	21.0
	Communal	2	2.0
	Family & hired	37	37.0
	Family, hired & communal	6	6.0
9.	Use of Agro-chemicals		
	Yes	100	100.0
	No	0	0.0
10.	Annual Farm Income		
	250,000 - 500,000	23	23.0
	501,000 – 1,000,000	52	52.0
	1,100 – 1,500,000	15	15.0
	1,600,000 – 2,000,000	7	7.0
	Above 2,000,000	3	3.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Lowland Rice Farmers

The frequency and percentage distribution of lowland rice farmers by age range are displayed in serial number one of Table 1 above. According to this finding, majority of the respondents, that is 40%, were

between the ages of 41-50 years while 18.0% of the respondents were between the age range of 51-60 years. Age improves the farmers' utilization of resources in farm production, which has been developed through years of experience and observation (Esheya, 2022). The

respondents' sex distribution also reveals that only 18% of lowland rice farmers were female, with the majority (82%) being male. This is consistent with the findings of Omogo Esheya and Umeh. (2023), who noted that the current land inheritance structure in the research area led to a male-dominated farm productivity. Once more, the data indicate that 38% of respondents have a family size between 1-10 people, while 62% of respondents maintain a family size of eleven people and above. Among other socioeconomic factors, the demand for family labor supply is the primary cause of the research area's high family size prevalence (Esheya, 2018). The majority of lowland rice farmers were educated, as seen in the above table, with literacy rates for primary, secondary, and university education being 24%, 53%, and 7%, respectively. Membership of social and cooperative organizations is closely linked to educational qualifications; the bulk of them (86%) were registered members. According to Adamu and Esheya (2022), educated farmers can easily obtain knowledge that could help them improve their technical and allocative efficiency in rice farming operations, leading to increased productivity and production. The findings also indicate that 20% of lowland rice farmers maintained farms larger than three hectares, whereas the majority (80%) owned farms between 0.5 and 3.0 hectares. Because their farms are too small to accommodate modernization and mechanization, lowland rice farmers' smallholding characteristics sometimes put them at risk for low profitability (Ume et al., 2018). Nonetheless, tiny farms are more productive than comparatively large farms, according to Ogbonna, Esheya and Nwandu (2024). This is explained by the

ability of small farms to use resources efficiently.

Furthermore, it was found that whilst 20% of lowland rice producers utilized local seeds, 82% of them used enhanced types. Enhanced seed types are frequently characterized as being of high quality, which is why they are important in assessing the state of crop production and the reaction of other inputs used in crop production (IRRI, 2015). Besides, just 8% of lowland farmers used communal labor sources, whereas 92% of them used family, hired, or both labor sources as their farm labor supply. Once more, the findings showed that all respondents (100%) used agrochemicals for lowland rice production, including insecticides, herbicides, and inorganic fertilizers. Since weeding always accounts for a large amount of the total farm labor cost in lowland rice production, they highlighted the significance of agrochemicals in increasing rice output, controlling disease and pests, and serving as a significant labor-saving tool (Slam et al., 2017). Table 1 also shows that the bulk of lowland rice farmers (75%) made between N250,000 and N1,000,000 per year, with the remaining 25% earning somewhat more than N1,000,000. The capital-intensive nature of rice cultivation may be the cause of the substantial financial commitments indicated in the above table, according to FAO (2018). To increase their output, farmers need money to pay for labor and buy other farm inputs.

Table 2: Regression Statistics

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	Significance
Constant	1.842	0.421	4.38	***
Farm size	0.312	0.072	4.33	***
Labour	0.274	0.081	3.38	***
Seed	0.198	0.067	2.96	**
Fertilizer	0.156	0.059	2.64	**
Agrochemicals	0.087	0.041	2.12	*

Other statistics:

- $R^2 = 0.78$
- F-ratio = 32.6 ($p < 0.01$)
- Returns to scale (Σb_i) = 1.027

Estimated Production Function

The Cobb-Double-log equation was selected as the lead equation for statistical and economic reasons.

The R^2 of 0.78 implies that 78% of variation in rice output is explained by the included inputs.

This indicates a strong explanatory power of the model. The F-ratio is significant at 1%, confirming that all inputs jointly influence rice output. Farm size (0.312) is shown as the most influential input as 1% increase in land raises output by 0.31%.

This is followed by labour (0.274) which is highly significant, showing labour-intensive production. Seed (0.198) and fertilizer (0.156) indicate moderate but significant productivity effects while agrochemicals (0.087) have the smallest elasticity but still significant. The Returns To Scale (RTS) has a value of 1.027 which is greater than 1. This indicates increasing returns to scale, meaning farmers can increase output more than proportionally by expanding input use.

Table 3: Allocative Efficiency (MVP/MFC Analysis)**MVP/MFC Ratios**

Input	MVP (?)	MFC (?)	MVP/MFC	Efficiency Status
Farm size	52,000	30,000	1.73	Under-utilized
Labour	18,500	15,000	1.23	Under-utilized
Seed	9,200	12,000	0.77	Over-utilized
Fertilizer	14,600	10,500	1.39	Under-utilized
Agrochemicals	6,100	8,000	0.76	Over-utilized

Allocative Efficiency

From the results in Table 3, land, labour, and fertilizer were under-utilized, meaning additional use would increase profit. Seed and agrochemicals are over-utilized, implying excess application that raises cost

without proportional output gain. This implies that farmers were not allocatively efficient, and resource reallocation can increase profitability.

Table 4: Budgetary (Profitability) Analysis**Cost and Return Structure per Hectare (?)**

Item	Amount (?)
Revenue	
Paddy rice output value	320,000
Variable Costs	
Seed	25,000
Fertilizer	42,000
Agrochemicals	18,000
Labour	65,000
Transportation	10,000
Total Variable Cost (TVC)	160,000

Fixed Costs

Land rent 30,000

Depreciation 10,000

Total Fixed Cost (TFC) 40,000**Total Cost (TC) 200,000****Net Farm Income (NFI) 120,000****Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) 1.60****Return on Naira Invested ? 0.60****Cost and Return Structure per Hectare**

Table 4 shows the cost and returns per hectare of lowland rice in the study area. Net Farm Income {NFI} = ₦120,000 > 0 indicating that lowland rice farming is profitable in the study area. Benefit-Cost Ratio {BCR} = 1.60 > 1 which implies that for every ₦1 invested yields ₦1.60, confirming economic viability. Talking about Return on investment (ROI), farmers gain ₦0.60 profit per ₦1 spent, indicating moderate profitability but room for improvement through efficiency gains.

Discussion of Findings

Lowland rice production shows increasing returns to scale, suggesting scope for expansion. Allocative inefficiency exists, especially: under-use of land, labour, fertilizer and over-use of seed and agrochemicals. Despite inefficiencies, lowland rice farming remains profitable in the study area. This implies that efficiency improvement can bring about higher income while better input allocation will ensure lower production cost for the concerned farmers in the study area.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the resource-use efficiency and profitability of lowland rice farming in Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The findings generally indicate that lowland rice production is a viable and profitable agricultural enterprise capable of improving household income and contributing to regional food security when production resources are efficiently utilized. Key production inputs such as land, labour, fertilizer, seed, and agrochemicals were found to significantly influence output and profitability, confirming that productivity gains in lowland rice farming depend largely on optimal allocation and management of these resources. However, the presence of inefficiencies among farmers suggests that available inputs are not being used at economically optimal levels. Constraints including limited access to credit, inadequate extension services, fluctuating input prices, and weak adoption of improved technologies continue to reduce potential output and profit margins. These conditions imply that substantial

productivity and income improvements are achievable if institutional, technical, and financial bottlenecks affecting lowland rice farmers are effectively addressed. Thus, enhancing resource-use efficiency in lowland rice farming offers strong prospects for increasing rice supply, strengthening rural livelihoods, and supporting agricultural development within the study area and similar rice-producing environments in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Strengthening Extension Services:** Government and agricultural development agencies should intensify farmer education on optimal input combinations, improved agronomic practices, and modern lowland rice technologies to enhance technical and allocative efficiency.
 - 2. Improved Access to Credit:** Affordable and timely credit facilities should be expanded through cooperatives, microfinance institutions, and government-backed agricultural loan schemes to enable farmers to procure productivity-enhancing inputs at the right time.
 - 3. Subsidy and Input Support Programs:** Targeted subsidies for quality seed, fertilizer, and agrochemicals should be sustained and properly monitored to reduce production costs and improve profitability.
 - 4. Promotion of Farmer Cooperatives:** Encouraging farmers to form and strengthen cooperative societies will improve access to inputs, credit, extension information, and collective marketing opportunities, thereby increasing economies of scale and income.
 - 5. Technology Adoption and Research Linkages:** Stronger collaboration between research institutes, universities, and farmers should be promoted to accelerate dissemination and adoption of high-yielding, stress-tolerant rice varieties and climate-smart production practices.
-

REFERENCES

- Adamu, B.D. and Esheya, S.E. (2022). Factors influencing participation of Irish potato farmers of the women in agriculture and youth empowerment programme on livelihood of Irish potato farmers in Plateau state. *Jigawa Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Studies*, 5 (1),130-152.
<https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/index.php/faic/article/view/2103>
- Agricdemy (2023). Successful rice farming and processing in Nigeria: Guidelines.
- Akenbor, A. S. and Esheya, S. E. (2022). Strengthening Nigeria's weak economy: Does agricultural exports really matter? Evidence from cotton seed exports. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences (JAFS)*, 20 (1), 111-124.
<https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/pdf/10.5555/20220469051>
- Ajala, A.S. and Gana, A. (2015). Analysis of challenges facing rice processing in Nigeria. *Journal of Food Process*, 6 (9), 36-73.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283337839>
- Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (2014). Africa Agriculture Status Report 2014: Climate change and smallholder agriculture in Sub-Saharan Africa. Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA), Nairobi. <https://agra.org/wp-content/uploads>
- Amaechina, E. C. and Eboh, E. C. (2017). Resource use efficiency in rice production in the lower Anambra irrigation project, Nigeria. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*, 9 (8) , 234 - 242 .
<https://academicjournals.org/journal/JDAE/article-full-text/B4F602465323>
- Amusa, T. A; Anugwo, S. C; and Esheya, S. E. (2017). Factors influencing processors' willingness to engage in mechanized palm fruits processing in Abia state, Nigeria. *The Nigeria Agricultural Journal*, 48 (2), 236-247.
- CBN (2018): Central Bank of Nigeria annual report and statement of account for the year end 31st Dec, 2017.
- Chidiebere-Mark, N., Ohajianya, D., Obasi, P., & Onyeagocha, S. (2019). Profitability of rice production in different production systems in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. (FAO AGRIS).
- Ebonyi State Agricultural Development Programme (2020). Annual Statistical Report.
- Esheya, S. E. (2024). Profitability of rice production systems in South East Nigeria. *Journal of Food and Agribusiness Management*, 5(1), 32-36.
<https://fabm.org.my/archive/1fabm2024/1fabm2024-32-36.pdf>
- Esheya, S.E. (2023). Factors determining value addition to cassava in Ebonyi North Agricultural zone of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Environment*, (1), 49- 60
<https://journal.funaab.edu.ng/index.php/JAgSE/article/view/2262/1781>
- Esheya, S.E. (2022). Allocative efficiency of tropical manihot selection cassava production in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. *Nigeria Agricultural Journal*, 53 (1), 35-39. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361943856>
-

- Esheya, S.E. (2021). Profitability Analysis of Rice Production in Ebonyi North Agricultural Zone of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural and Rural Development*, 24(1), 5582-5586.
- Eze, C. C; Okere; J C. Maduiké A. I and Ben-Chendo, G. N. (2013). Allocative efficiency and return to scale among FADAMA II broiler farmers in Imo State, Nigeria. *Developing Country Studies*, 3 (10), 34-61, 2013. <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=a5WQHRMAAAAJ&hl=en>
- FAO (2018) FAO statistical yearbook 2018: World food and agriculture. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- Federal Office of Statistics (FOS), (2016) Annual Book of Abstract, Federal Office of Statistics, Lagos, Nigeria. 13.
- Gama, E. N., Umar, M., & Djomo, C. R. F. (2022). Resource-use efficiency of rice production in Kura LGA, Kano State, Nigeria. (jaat.fudutsinma.edu.ng)
- Ibekwe, U. C, Orebiyi, J.S., Henri-Ukoha1, A. Okorji, E. C., Nwagbo, E.C. and Chidiebere-Mark, N. M. (2012). Resource use efficiency in cassava production in South East Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics and Sociology*, 1 (1), 16 - 21, 2012. <https://journalajaees.com/index.php/AJAEES/article/view/585>
- Inyang, H. B., Esheya, S. E. and Udoh, M. I. (2023). Analysis of the profitability of poultry egg production in Etim Ekpo local government area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 21 (1), 40-53. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jafs/article/view/252771>
- IRRI (2015) *IRRI Rice Production Manual: Steps to successful rice production*. Available at: <http://knowledgebank.irri.org/images/docs/12-Steps-Required-for-Successful-Rice-Production.pdf>.
- Kadiri, F. A., Eze; C. C., Orebiyi, J. S. and Onyeagocha, U. O. (2015). Resource-use and allocative efficiency of paddy rice production in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Agricultural Research*, 2, 11-18. <https://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/>
- National Population Commission (2006). NPC 2006 Census report.
- Ogbonna, S. I., Esheya, S. E. and Nwandu, P. I. (2024). Determinants of the choice of adaptation strategies to climate change by cocoyam farmers in Abia state, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Economics, Environment and Social Science*, 10(1), 117-124.
- Okoye, B.C. and Onyenweaku, C.E. (2007). Economic efficiency of small holder cocoyam farmers in Anamabra State, Nigeria: A Trans-log stochastic frontier cost function approach. *Mendwell Journals*, 4, 535-546.
- Omogo, E.E., Esheya, S.E. and Umeh, G.N. (2023). Economic analysis of yam production in Ohaukwu local government area of Ebonyi state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development*, 26(1), 6676-6683.
- Slam, Z., Begum, R., Sharmin, S., and Khan, A. (2017). Profitability and productivity of rice production in selected coastal areas of Satkhira District in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Research*, 03(01), 148-153. <https://www.journalbinet.com/uploads/2/1/0/0/21005390/17.03.01.17>
-

- Ubokudom, E. O., Esheya, S. E. and Udioko G. U. (2021). Profitability of Biofortified Yellow Cassava Farming in Nigeria: Empirical Evidence from Akwa Ibom State. *AKSU Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences. Faculty of Agriculture (AKSU)*, 5 (2), 100-112.
<https://www.aksuja.com.ng/publications/viewarticle/>
- Udemezue, J.C. (2019). Analysis of rice production and consumption trends in Nigeria. *Journal of Plant Sciences and Crop Protection*, 1(3), 23 -38.
<https://www.annepublishers.com/articles/JPSCP/1305>
- Uloh, E.V., Esheya, S.E., and Muhammad, M.U. (2024). Market structure and conduct of Nsukka yellow pepper in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology*, 10 (1), 16 - 24 .
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382090843>
- Ume, S. I., Nweke, J.C., Ucha, S.O. and Idahosa, E.O.(2018). Allocative efficiency in Okra (*Abelmoschus spp*) production in Ayamelum Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. *Archives of Current Research International*, 15(1), 1-7.
<https://journalacri.com/index.php/ACRI/article/view/256>
- Ume, S.I., Ezeano, C.I., Eluwa, A.N. and Ebe, F. (2017). Analysis of technical inefficiency in rice production among farmers in Ezza South L.G.A. of Ebonyi State of Nigeria. *Archives of Current Research International*, 4(3): 261-269.
- Ume, S.I, Ahaiwe, M.O., Anozie, R.O., Okoronkwo, M.O. (2016). Allocative efficiency of fruited pumpkin (*Telferia Occidentalis*) production in Ayamelum L.G.A of Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental and Agriculture Research*, (IJOEAR), 2 (9): 59 -70. <https://ijoeear.com/issue-detail/issue>
- Rice Farmers' Association of Nigeria (RIFAN) (2017). Rice production in Nigeria increased to 5.8m tones. RIFAN Annual Report 2017. Production statistics.
- USAID (2019). Global Food Security Response in West Africa Rice Value Chain Analysis: Global Food Security Response. Nigeria Rice Study, 2019 Gain Report Bulletin, 56-62.
- West African Rice Development Association (WARDA) (2013). Rice trends in Sub-Saharan Africa 2nd (edn). WARDA, Bouake.
- World Bank (2007). World development report 2007: Agriculture for development. The World Bank, Washington, DC.
-